

Endo- and ectoparasites of the Philippine rice field rat, *Rattus tanezumi* Temminck, on PhilRice farms

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The Philippine rice field rat, *Rattus tanezumi* Temminck, is one of the principal pre- and postharvest pests of rice and other agricultural crops. This species usually thrives in lowland and upland rice fields but can also be found in or near places of human habitation. They damage agricultural crops and also serve as reservoir hosts for diseases of certain human and domestic animals caused by helminths, protozoans, and microbes.

Many endoparasites infecting the different viscera of *R. tanezumi* belong to taxonomic groups Nematoda (roundworms), Cestoda (tapeworms), and Trematoda (flukes). The more important ones are those that are transmissible to humans. In contrast, there have been few reports on the ectoparasites that infest these rats. These are the mites, ticks, and fleas, some of which may serve as vectors of microbial infections to humans and domestic animals.

Rattus tanezumi is an alternative meat source for the rural folk. Rat meat is a favorite accompaniment to alcoholic beverages during drinking sprees. Unknowingly, some zoonotic infections can be transmitted to humans through improperly cooked rat meat and viscera, accidental wound contamination with rat urine, or rat bites during handling and pre-cooking preparations.

When rats frequent human abodes, they can contaminate objects such as clothing and dishes

with their ectoparasites. Though they have low host specificity, these arthropods can infect humans and domestic animals—their bites may result in microbial infections or hypersensitive reactions.

In this study, we identified, according to viscera, the endoparasites and ectoparasites affecting *R. tanezumi* and described their mode of transmission to humans. The monthly prevalence of infected *R. tanezumi*, by sex and endo- and ectoparasite species, was also determined.

Rattus tanezumi collected from PhilRice rice fields, irrigation systems, and rat burrows were brought to the laboratory for identification. They were sorted according to sex, weight, and sexual maturity. The weight of male and female rats ranged from 80 to 150 g and from 100 to 150 g, respectively. The ectoparasites were collected immediately after killing the rat. Chloroform was used to kill the ectoparasites on the dead rats. The parasites were combined from the rat into a white, enameled pan. The rat's internal organs were removed and dissected for microscopic examination of endoparasites. Parasite specimens were transferred into 1.5-mL microtubes containing 95% ethanol for storage and for permanent mounting after identification. The monthly prevalence of infected *R. tanezumi* was calculated.

Six species of endoparasites and three species of ectoparasites infected *R. tanezumi* on PhilRice farms (Table 1). (Voucher specimens, accession numbers 2006-30 to 37, are deposited in the Parasite Collection, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Philippines.) The endoparasites were found in the liver, lungs, pulmonary arteries, duodenum, and small intestines. The ectoparasites, on the other hand, were detected in the skin and, in a few cases, in the small intestines because of accidental ingestion. A majority of the parasites identified were zoonotic to humans. The mode of transmission varied between parasites.

Nematode infections between rat sexes were similar, except for *Angiostrongylus cantonensis* (Table 2). In August, *A. cantonensis* emerged. The incidence of *Nippostrongylus muris* was observed to be higher throughout the study period. *Rodentolepis* spp. (= *Hymenolepis* spp.), *Raillietina garrisoni*, and *Taenia taeniaeformis* (= *Strobilocercus fasciolaris*) infections were much lower than other endoparasitic infections. *Euparyphium* spp. infections were higher than those of cestodes. The kind of food sources consumed at a particular time is probably related to infections of endoparasites. All *R. tanezumi* samples were infected with *Liponyssus bacoti* (= *Ornithonyssus bacoti*), but few animals had the

two species of rat louse (*Polyplax* spp. and *Hoplopleura* spp.).

A majority of the parasites observed in this study are zoonotic to human beings and infect do-

mestic animals. The best protection is to maintain environmental sanitation and to discriminate in the cooking and consumption of rat meat. Hand washing, good hy-

giene with food preparation, and insect management are equally important in preventing parasite transmission cycles.

Table 1. Endo- and ectoparasite(s) observed in the organs of *R. tanezumi* and their mode of transmission to humans, PhilRice, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, June-December 2005.

Parasite identified	Common name	Organ of origin	Zoonotic to humans	Mode of transmission to humans
<i>Taenia taeniaeformis</i> (= <i>Strobilocercus fasciolaris</i>)	Tapeworm	Liver	?	Ingestion of raw liver containing viable larvae
<i>Rodentolepis</i> (= <i>Hymenolepis</i> spp.) (= <i>Vampirolepis</i> spp.)	Tapeworm	Duodenum	Yes	Accidental ingestion of intermediate host—beetles infected with parasite eggs (<i>H. diminuta</i>) or direct ingestion of parasite eggs from infected humans (<i>H. nana</i>)
<i>Raillietina garrisoni</i>	Tapeworm	Small intestines	Yes	Accidental ingestion of intermediate host—beetles infected with parasite eggs
<i>Angiostrongylus cantonensis</i>	Rat lungworm (nematode)	Lungs, pulmonary arteries	Yes	Ingestion of improperly cooked land snail/golden apple snail (<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>) carrying the larvae of the parasite
<i>Nippostrongylus muris</i>	Roundworm	Small intestines	No	—
<i>Euparyphium</i> spp.	Fluke	Small intestines	Yes	Ingestion of infected land snails containing cercariae
<i>Liponyssus bacoti</i> (= <i>Ornithonyssus bacoti</i>)	Tropical mite	Skin	Yes	Ingestion can transmit <i>Pasteurella tularensis</i>
<i>Polyplax</i> spp.	Rat louse	Skin	No	—
<i>Hoplopleura</i> spp.	Rat louse	Skin	No	—

Table 2. Monthly prevalence (%) of infected *R. tanezumi*, by endo- and ectoparasitic preference, PhilRice, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, June-December 2005.

Sex	Month	Endoparasites ^a						Ectoparasites	
		Nematoda		Cestoda			Trematoda	Tropical mite	Rat louse
		A ^b	B	C	D	E	F		
Male	June (24) ^c	0	91.7	8.3	4.2	8.3	29.2	100	—
	July (45)	0	100	8.9	0	2.2	68.9	100	—
	August (7)	14.3	100	28.6	14.3	14.3	57.1	100	—
	September (7)	0	100	28.6	14.3	28.6	71.4	100	—
	October (6)	0	100	0	0	0	33.3	100	—
	November (11)[3] ^d	0	100	9.1	0	0	54.6	100	0
	December (8)[4]	0	100	0	0	0	87.5	100	25.0
Female	June (23)	0	100	4.3	0	26.1	60.9	100	—
	July (43)	0	97.7	16.3	2.3	7.0	67.4	100	—
	August (9)	22.2	100	11.1	0	11.1	44.4	100	—
	September (11)	27.3	90.9	18.2	9.1	45.5	81.8	100	—
	October (14)	7.1	92.9	14.3	14.3	21.4	71.4	100	—
	November (9)[3]	22.2	100	0	0	0	88.9	100	33.3
	December (8)[4]	0	100	0	0	0	100	100	0
Juvenile with hair	November [6]	—	—	—	—	—	—	100	83.3
	December [5]	—	—	—	—	—	—	100	40.0

^aA = *Angiostrongylus cantonensis*, B = *Nippostrongylus muris*, C = *Hymenolepis* spp., D = *Raillietina garrisoni*, E = *Taenia taeniaeformis*, F = *Euparyphium* spp. ^bThe sex bias of infection of *A. cantonensis* was for female rats. ^cTotal number of rats examined. ^dTotal number of rats examined for two species of ectoparasitic rat louse.